

Open Citation Data for Educational Research

Verena Weimer¹, Muhammad Ahsan Shahid², Tamara Heck¹,
Thomas Oerder¹, Philipp Mayr², Christoph Schindler¹

¹ *DIPF*

² *GESIS*

Purpose and Goal

Citations are an important element of scientific communication, as they show relationships between scientific publications, research data and their authors within the scientific community. They therefore serve researchers as an important tool in their search for relevant literature, a strategy called chaining (Ellis, 1989). In addition, citation data is used in bibliometric and scientometric studies as evidence of internal scientific communication for the self-reflection of a discipline, for the evaluation and control of research performance and for research management (van Raan, 2019; Ball, 2020). In the past, the collection, processing and provision of scientific citation data was in the hands of a few commercial providers, such as Clarivate (Web of Science) and Elsevier (Scopus). Their use is based on licenses, which results in two major problems: Firstly, the commercial citation databases are subject to a fee and are not openly accessible. Secondly, those citation databases do not cover all disciplines to the same extent. As a result, these citation databases are only suitable for searching for literature and evaluating research to a very limited extent. This applies above all to the social sciences and humanities, which include almost all educational research disciplines, such as educational research and sociology (Moed, 2005; Singleton et al., 2015). Studies also show that reference lists in those databases are missing or are insufficient (Martín-Martín et al., 2018; Visser, van Eck, Waltman, 2021; Chi, 2014). In summary, educational research lacks exhaustive and high-quality citation data to be applied to improve literature search and disciplinary bibliometric studies.

Current research projects and network activities aim to contribute to open and networked citation data in science (Backes et al., 2024). The Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC) is an association of various stakeholders, such as scientific publishers and researchers, with the aim of making scientific citation data openly available and machine-readable (Heibi et al., 2024). This makes publications easier to find, specialist information services can offer advanced search functions, and the linking of topics and interdisciplinary collaborations can be explicitly established and made visible via knowledge graphs (Hocker et al., 2020; Hocker et al., 2019). The main aim of Open Citations is to promote open citation data that is not subject to license rights, as is the case with the commercial citation database providers Web of Science and Scopus, for example. Another initiative for open citations is OpenAlex, which published the first version of its open catalog in January 2022. OpenAlex is intended to provide a basis for standardized scientific entities in order to show complete and correct relations between them. OpenAlex is thus dedicated to the challenge of standardizing scientific metadata. This is an important basis for the complete and correct recording and extraction of citation data.

The project "Open Citation Data for Educational Research" (OFFZIB) aligns with those initiatives and aims to extract citation data from open access publications in educational research and make them available via the central national German Education Index (FIS Bildung). To reach this goal, we need to adapt an extraction algorithm to best perform with educational literature data and to establish new workflows to maintain the provision of the extracted data when the project has ended.

Method

The project has three major tasks. To extract citation data, the tool OUTCITE will be trained on publications from the German Education Index open access repository peDOCS (~ 28,000 publications) (task 1). The German Education Index is a comprehensive source for educational research. Almost 30 cooperating documentation institutions compile the literature database jointly and index specialist literature on the education system and its research systematized. The extraction tool will be integrated into the system environment of the German Education Portal to extract citation data from future publications (task 2). To actively contribute to the development of a transdisciplinary and transnational citation inventory beyond the specific subject communities of educational research, the citation data will be passed on to the Open Citations Initiative. For a sustainable structural effect of the citation data production, an embedding is to be created in the production process of the German Education Index (task 3).

Expected Results

So far, the OUTCITE algorithm (Hosseini et al., 2019) extracted citation data from German-language social science publications, resulting in solid F-scores for various tasks (compare Backes et al., 2024 for details) and better results for the corpus tested compared to other approaches (Körner et al., 2017). The tool includes three core steps: An algorithm processes the publication text and records places with citations. Another algorithm breaks down the reference strings at the end of a publication into corresponding semantic units (author, title, year, etc.). The recorded citations in the text are then linked to the references. A challenge with educational literature data is the heterogeneity of citation formats (Powley & Dale, 2007) in reference lists as well as in the texts, ranging from in-text citations in APA style to numbered citations or footnote citations. The literature will be analyzed according to the different citation styles to best train the algorithm. The evaluation of the algorithm will be based on a data subset considering the different disciplines in educational research, the document types and the publication year to cover a broad range of diverse citation styles.

The project started in January 2025. First results on the performance of the extraction algorithm and the different citation styles in educational research will be presented and discussed in the poster.

References

- Backes, T., Iurshina, A., Shahid, M. A., & Mayr, P. (2024). Comparing Free Reference Extraction Pipelines. *International Journal on Digital Libraries*, 25(4), 841–853. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-024-00404-6>, Preprint
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10582214>

- Ball, R. (Hrsg.). (2020). Handbook Bibliometrics. De Gruyter Saur. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110646610>
- Chi, P.-S. (2014). Which role do non-source items play in the social sciences? A case study in political science in Germany. *Scientometrics*, 101(2), 1195–1213. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-014-1433-1>
- Ellis, D. (1989). A behavioural approach to information retrieval system design. *Journal of Documentation*, 45(3), 171-212. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb026843>
- Heibi, I., Moretti, A., Peroni, S., Soricetti, M. (2024): The OpenCitations Index. *Scientometrics* 129(12). doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.02321>
- Hocker, J.; Veja, C., Schindler, C.; Rittberger, M., (2019): Establishing semantic research graphs in humanities' research practice. In: Draude, C., Lange, M. & Sick, B. (Hrsg.), *INFORMATIK 2019: 50 Jahre Gesellschaft für Informatik – Informatik für Gesellschaft (Workshop-Beiträge)*. Bonn: Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V. (S. 169-174). https://doi.org/10.18420/inf2019_ws18
- Hocker, J.; Schindler, C.; Rittberger, M. (2020): Participatory design for ontologies: a case study of an open science ontology for qualitative coding schemas, *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 72 No. 4, pp. 671-685. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-11-2019-0320>
- Hosseini, A., Ghavimi, B., Boukhers, Z., & Mayr, P. (2019). EXCITE - A toolchain to extract, match and publish open literature references. *Proceedings of the ACM/IEEE Joint Conference on Digital Libraries 2019*, 432–433. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JCDL.2019.00105>
- Körner, M., Ghavimi, B., Mayr, P., Hartmann, H., & Staab, S. (2017). Evaluating reference string extraction using line-based conditional random fields: A case study with German language publications. In M. Kirikova, K. Nørvåg, G. A. Papadopoulos, J. Gamper, R. Wrembel, J.
- Darmont, & S. Rizzi (Eds.), *New Trends in Databases and Information Systems*. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-67162-8_15
- Martín-Martín, A., Orduna-Malea, E., Thelwall, M., & Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2018). Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus: A systematic comparison of citations in 252 subject categories. *JOURNAL of INFORMETRICS*, 12(4), 1160-1177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2018.09.002>
- Moed, H. F. (2005). *Citation analysis in research evaluation*. Information Science and Knowledge Management: Bd. 9. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-3714-7>
- Powley, B., & Dale, R. (2007). Evidence-based information extraction for high accuracy citation and author name identification. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Natural Language Processing and Knowledge Engineering*. <https://web.science.mq.edu.au/~rdale/publications/papers/2007/62.pdf>
- Powley, B., & Dale, R. (2007). High accuracy citation extraction and named entity recognition for a heterogeneous corpus of academic papers. In *2007 International Conference on Natural Language Processing and Knowledge Engineering: IEEE NLP-KE 2007*; Beijing, China, 30 August - 1 September 2007 (pp. 119–124). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/NLPKE.2007.4368021>

- Singleton, K., Kuhberg-Lasson, V., Sondergeld, U., & Schultheiß, J. (2015). Publikationen der Bildungsforschung. In A. Botte, U. Sondergeld, & M. Rittberger (Eds.), *Monitoring Bildungsforschung: Befunde aus dem Forschungsprojekt "Entwicklung und Veränderungsdynamik eines heterogenen sozialwissenschaftlichen Feldes am Beispiel der Bildungsforschung"* (pp. 69–106). Klinkhardt.
- Van Raan, Anthony (2019): *Measuring Science: Basic Principles and Application of Advanced Bibliometrics*. In: Glänzel, Wolfgang; Moed, Henk F.; Schmoch, Ulrich; Thelwall, Mike: *Springer Handbook of Science and Technology Indicators*. Switzerland: Springer.
- Visser, M., van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2021). Large-scale comparison of bibliographic data sources: Scopus, Web of Science, Dimensions, Crossref, and Microsoft Academic. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 2(1), 20–41. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00112